

The Factors Affecting the US Withdrawal from JCPOA and Its Impact on the Political and Economic Security of the Islamic Republic of Iran

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Abstract:

The purpose of this study is to investigate the factors affecting the US withdrawal from the Joint Comprehensive Plan of Action (JCPOA) and its impact on the political and economic security of the Islamic Republic of Iran and the findings of the article, which was obtained by using the theory of realist hegemony and written and virtual sources and descriptive analytical method that is the restoration of American domination in the form of the rejection of Obama's theory, the rupture of convergence among the Shiite resistance front, the security of the Zionist regime, the foundations of Trump's foreign policy, the persistence of the threatening nature of Iran after JCPOA, Israel and Saudi Arabia on threatening Iran, their interpretation of the role of JCPOA in strengthening Iran's regional presence and ignoring this issue in the text of JCPOA and internally, the post-JCPOA action of the Islamic Republic of Iran should be among the key variables in Donald Trump's decision on the withdrawal of the United States from JCPOA.

Keywords: USA, JCPOA, Political Security, Economic Security, Iran

Introduction:

With the arrival of Donald J. Trump in the White House, American political approaches have been entirely selective and based on American national interests. Basically, Trump believes that the United States should be willing to cut ties with anyone and any country it needs. He also explicitly opposes the role of US global leadership and clearly questions US international obligations. Trump has previously stated in his speech to Congress: "My duty is not to represent the world, my duty is to represent the United States" (Soleimanzadeh et al., 2016: 275).

The issue of the decline of American hegemony has been raised many times by Republicans, so much so that Trump in his election debates, widely criticizing Obama's performance accused him of compromising with the revolutionary governments of the region, especially the Islamic Republic of Iran. On the other hand, Obama's policies were considered by Republican leaders to be the best opportunity for the growing development of terrorism in the West Asian region. Iran, meanwhile, has been blamed for the failure of Saudi military policies in the Yemeni crisis and Ansar al-Islam missile strikes on Saudi oil positions, the capture of several US naval personnel by Revolutionary Guards in the Persian Gulf, which is a heavy psychological burden for Americans. In addition to threatening to close the Strait of Hormuz, the world's oil transit bottleneck, he convinced Trump that the resumption of US hegemony in the Persian Gulf region posed a significant obstacle to Iran. Therefore, in the first step, Trump rejected the policies of the Obama era. Trump has escalated tensions with his one-sided and pragmatic policies toward the Islamic Republic of Iran and some other countries that US politicians believe were at the center of evil. (Stokes, 2018: 138)

Trump's administration is the most radical in the United States for at least the last two decades, and it houses the most militant and extremist Republicans. They are far more ideological than the Obama administration. In this group, the majority are with the generals, and in their mental background, most of them have a prominent military option on any issue. Another feature of the Trump administration is that these people have a hostile attitude towards the Islamic Republic of Iran. Most of the generals who have been influential in Trump's foreign policy have been in Iran's strategic environment, including in Iraq and Afghanistan, and believe that Iran's policies and actions are a major factor in the US failure in those two countries. They have a significant enmity towards Iran. At the head of them was Michael Flynn, whose term was very short and he had to resign due to his connection with the Russian embassy. First Vice President Mike Pence, Rex Tillerson, who was later replaced by CIA Director Mike Pompeo; US Secretary of Defense Gen. James Mattis; General McMaster, who

later replaced John Bolton; These countries are the most important people in the United Nations who are very influential in shaping US foreign policy and national security strategy against Iran (Berman, 2017: 18).

From this perspective, the logic of American foreign policy approaches realism. The logic of realism is very military-oriented and considers military power and the use of force as inevitable consequences of the nature of world politics (Kalahan, 2008: 238)

Examining Trump's declared policies and actions it can be argued that he is in the best position to follow the new isolationism. Neo-modernism wants to end with the reduction of some foreign policy commitments, but at the same time agrees with the continuation of some of them and proposes the acceptance of some new commitments (Smith et al., 2016: 16).

In other words, modernism is a kind of selective internationalism, not absolute isolationism. According to this policy, modernism is a profit-oriented foreign policy with a kind of autonomous strategy and has a high ability to adapt to realism. On the other hand, neo-paganism pursues a kind of non-aligned diplomacy in the field of foreign policy, frees the United States from the chain of troublesome international organizations, treaties and restores American sovereignty and on the other hand realism of more freedom of action provides for the United States to act in sensitive situations. Because Trump's approach is instrumental in calculating the national interest of the United States, his administration often first assesses the costs of a committed foreign policy and isolationist policies, and then devises a foreign policy that serves the national interest and Be vital to America (Soleimanzadeh et al., 2018: 15).

"The oversight power of international inspectors is limited," "some parts of the agreement are not permanent," and "Iran has not adhered to the spirit of the agreement," he has repeatedly said, rooted in the US president's view of international agreements. "Trump's foreign policy has found its subject, and that is the exit doctrine," wrote the chairman of the Council on Foreign Relations and one of the most prominent advisers and thinkers in the field of American foreign policy on his Twitter page. The United States has abandoned or threatened to withdraw from important international treaties, including the Trans-Pacific Treaty, the Paris Climate Change Agreement, NAFTA, UNESCO, and the UN Security Council and JCPOA (Hass, 2017: 9).

The decline of US hegemony has been repeatedly raised by Republicans, with Trump widely criticizing Obama in his election debates, accusing him of compromising with the region's revolutionary governments, particularly the Islamic Republic of Iran. On the other hand, Obama's policies were considered by Republican leaders to be the best opportunity for the growing development of terrorism in the West Asian region. In the meantime, Iran was considered the first center of accusations (Stokes, 2018: 138)

The failure of Saudi military policies in the Yemeni crisis and Ansarullah rocket attacks on Saudi oil positions, the capture of several US Marines by the Revolutionary Guards in the Persian Gulf, which brought a heavy psychological burden to the Americans, along with the threat of closing the Strait of Hormuz as the world's oil transit bottleneck convinced Trump that the resumption of US hegemony in the Persian Gulf region was facing an important obstacle called Iran. So in the first place, Trump rejected the policies of the Obama era.

Ineffectiveness of sanctions against the Islamic Republic of Iran in the aftermath:

By pursuing a liberal internationalist approach, Obama sought to strengthen the US position in the international arena and turn it into a multilateral hegemony compared to the time of George W. Bush, when the US played an emperor role. (David & Grondin, 2016: 222)

One of the most important approaches of Trump, both during the election campaign with the Democrats and after the presidential election, has been to criticize and reject the policies of the Democrats, especially Barack Obama, regarding the issue of negotiations with Iran (Thompson, 2018: 2).

On the other hand, while the Obama administration's sanctions policy has been based more on the motivation of Iran to adhere to international rules and norms, the Trump administration's main motivation is to advance the maximum of US national interests regardless of international legal frameworks and restrictions. From this perspective, accepting JCPOA was an effective policy for the Obama administration, because it harmonized Iran's nuclear policy with international norms, but it was considered ineffective for the Trump administration, arguing that it has no significant benefit for the United States (Ghanbarloo, 2018: 77).

But Trump has repeatedly said that Barack Obama's policies not only did not impose restrictions on Iran, but also paved the way for Iran's growing military power in the region and its influence in West Asia. Trump's arguments in this regard have been such as missile equipment, military support for Shiite militias in the region, and the vast ideological influence of the Islamic Republic of Iran. Therefore, Trump has sought to achieve some of the most important goals by intensifying aggressive approaches against the Islamic Republic of Iran, especially after the abolition of JCPOA:

1. Destroying Obama's legacy of compromise and tolerance with the Islamic Republic of Iran in order to prevent Iran's growing influence in the region;
2. Incitement of regional allies, especially Bin Salman and Netanyahu against Iran;
3. Preventing investment in Iran and its economic development;
4. Achieving the dollars of the rich kings of the Persian Gulf. (Alcaro, 2018: 14)

- Common idea and understanding of the Iranian threat

JCPOA, like any other international agreement in the international anarchic world that relies on the comparative advantage of nations, has had unintended consequences, as the "logic of undesirable consequences" explains, no form of contract whether coercive or voluntary In international politics cannot be free from weaknesses, and in addition, the logic of adverse consequences is so strong that even the most definite results, such as unilateral agreements after victories and military conquests after defeating enemies, cannot be considered as having absolute benefits for the conquering country (Mousavian and Hosseini, 2016: 2).

Based on this, it seems that the role of Trump's Middle East approach and the formation of a kind of triangular alliance between the United States, Israel and Saudi Arabia can be considered as a central factor in the withdrawal of the United States from the UN Security Council. After JCPOA, Iran has achieved opportunities and benefits that have inevitably led to an increase in its influence and power in the region. Removing Iran's economic barriers and agreeing to its official presence in regional crises increased Iran's position and power in the region. This is a threat to other countries, especially Iran's regional rivals (Israel and Saudi Arabia, and the supra-regional hegemon, the United States). The reason for this is that these countries are unaware of their regional rival's intentions which are now a little stronger and increase of its military power which in the future can be considered a serious threat to the influence and power of Iran's regional rivals. (Salehi and Faramarz Manesh, 2016: 7).

So it seems natural that countermeasures should be taken to neutralize this, and that the persuasion of the supra-regional hegemon was aimed at exiting Iran, the JCPOA. It should be noted that what forms the main framework of Trump's Middle East policy. Their perception and understanding is about the increasing power-making factors of the Islamic Republic of Iran in the region in the post-JCPOA atmosphere. Such an approach can also be found well among Trump's regional allies, as it can be acknowledged that Saudi Arabia and Israel do not consider JCPOA as a factor in increasing regional stability by eliminating the risk of war, but as a factor in increasing Iran's power factors. In the region and a factor in increasing the threat of Iran. Thus, the formation of a common understanding between Saudi Arabia, Israel and the United States on the threat of Iran, their interpretation of the role of JCPOA in strengthening Iran's regional presence and ignoring this issue in the text of JCPOA should be among the main reasons for the US withdrawal. Considered a nuclear agreement (Souri, 2018: 2).

According to American critics, according to JCPOA, Iran's enrichment facility will continue to operate, the Islamic Republic of Iran will continue to research and develop to produce new generation centrifuges, and at the end of 15 to 25 years and the completion of an important part of the commitments, it can use these new technologies to promote the nuclear industry. The nuclear deal recognizes Iran as a country on the verge of nuclear. Some countries in the region are concerned that the success of the Islamic Republic of Iran in concluding the nuclear issue in negotiations with major world powers, will make this country strong and strengthen its role and influence in the region (Nawazani, Ghasemi and Farsai, 2015: 13).

For this reason, the global opponents of JCPOA are very angry about this. These individuals believe that because a significant portion of Iran's commitments will soon expire and restrictions on Iran's nuclear activities

will be lifted, the United States will put itself in a worse position in practice in the coming years by dismantling the sanctions regime.

Contrary to initial expectations, JCPOA not only did not ease regional competition, but also intensified tensions between Iran and regional rivals.

The nuclear deal is a form of paradoxical restriction in which Iran maintains its weapons capacity and, in return, the United States and its partners try to prevent Iran from using this capacity (Singh, 2015).

Eventually, along with extensive lobbying and other secondary variables, it paved the way for the US withdrawal from the United States, which is discussed below.

First; under the agreement, Iran's nuclear infrastructure will not be dismantled. So those regional rivals who are worried about Iran acquiring a nuclear weapon should be concerned about the possibility of Iran cheating, backing away from the deal, and reducing its nuclear escape time. Because with the end of JCPOA's life, most of the restrictions on Iran's nuclear activities as well as international monitoring will be lifted. From the neighbors' view point, Iran will be able to provide technical preparations for acquiring a nuclear weapon in a short period of time. As long as these countries are skeptical of Iran's hegemonic intentions, they cannot be indifferent to the consequences of Iran's acquisition of a nuclear weapon; although this possibility has been delayed.

Second; If the United States could stand as a reliable ally for weaker actors alongside these countries against a nuclear Iran, their fears of a possible Iranian nuclear weapon would be greatly reduced, but from their view point, the Nuclear agreement showed that by ignoring the Obama administration's call for Iran to suspend all nuclear activities, the United States has in practice shown its willingness to compromise with Iran at the expense of its allies. (Sick, 2016)

Third; According to Saudi Arabia, Iran's acquisition of a nuclear weapon cannot be measured without considering the competition of these powers for leadership of the Islamic world and, in the geopolitical language, the heartland of Islamic powers in Asia and Africa. Putting Iran on the brink of nuclear weapons production and its success in multilateral negotiations with the great powers, has been able to place Iran as a worthy power to lead the Islamic world and put Iran in a situation where the West has implicitly accepted its role as a disruptor of the vast expanse from Lebanon to Yemen. (Barnaby, 1989)

Fourth, Israel also considers some of Iran's restrictions in the coming years to be among the disadvantages of this agreement and has repeatedly demanded that they be made permanent. They refer to these clauses in JCPOA, whose restrictions will be lifted in the coming years, as "JCPOA sunset" clauses. According to the clause, Iran could increase the number of uranium enrichment centrifuges to more than the current ceiling (5,060) after 10 years from the implementation of the nuclear deal. However, even after 15 years, it can increase its allowable limit (300 kg) of its less enriched uranium reserves. Netanyahu, meanwhile, claims that lifting the ban would return Iran to zero. By magnification, Israel imagines the Islamic Republic of Iran as a threat and a source of insecurity for itself, and by identifying it as an enemy seeking the destruction of Israel (another dangerous one), it has taken special measures and by definition an exceptional case, JCPOA considered his inefficiency and restraint against Iran's nuclear program ineffective and sought to sabotage and persuade the United States to withdraw.

So, in order to ensure its survival in this tense region, Israel seeks to increase its power and achieve regional hegemony.

Therefore, the further weakening and isolation of Iran in the region is completely in line with Israel's security goals (Ghavam and Imani, 2011: 90)

Israel's efforts with the United States in this direction are rooted in a theoretical and important logic in international politics, which is to prevent the emergence of regional hegemons (Nasr, 2006).

- Creating gradual damage and divergence between the Shiite Resistance Front:

The third reason for Trump's intensification of aggressive approaches against the Islamic Republic of Iran is the creation of a kind of gradual divergence between the Shiites and the Resistance Front in the region. The fact is that with the emergence of the ISIS terrorist group and the fall of important cities in Iraq and Syria, the Islamic Republic of Iran, in addition to logistical support to its allies, the Assad governments in Syria and Haidar al-

Abadi in Iraq, not only with many problems the achievements of the terrorist group, Rather it paved the way for a stronger Shiite coalition in the region. The formation of al-Shabaab militants in Iraq, the growing expansion of Lebanese Hezbollah missile and military power, the new structuring of Shiite militias in Afghanistan, and the broad coalition with Ansar al-in Yaman changed the region in favor of Iran, while the rise and consistency of ISIS was formed primarily with the aim of degenerating the Shiite governments of the region such as Iraq and Syria (O'Driscoll & Van Zoonen, 2017: 24)

After the relative annihilation of Takfiris ISIS, the United States and other regional allies realized that the rise of ISIS had the opposite effect, not only that the desired goals were not achieved, but that the convergence of Shiites in the region had reached its highest level in at least a hundred years. It should not be forgotten that many Iraqi military theorists, such as Abu Mahdi al-Mohandes, Sheikh Akram al-Kaabi, commander of the Najba movement in Iraq, the books of Hezbollah in Iraq, and many other militias operating in the region are all in full conformity with Iranian politics. Also, the popularity of Iranian military commanders, especially the Islamic Revolutionary Guard Corps such as Sardar Soleimani in the region, especially Iraq and Syria, has reached its highest level at least in the last four decades (Parello- Plesner, 2018: 16)

Ensuring the security of the Zionist regime: The fourth reason for the intensification of Trump's hostile policies against the Islamic Republic of Iran should be considered as supporting the security and identity of the Jews, especially the Zionist regime. The resistance of some countries in the region against US hegemony centered on Iran is one of the most important political crises in West Asia (Middle East) (Scazzieri, 2017: 6).

In this regard, the first point is the Zionist regime, which as a strategic ally of the United States and the guardian of its interests in West Asia, is exposed to a serious threat posed by the Islamic resistance, especially by the Islamic Revolution of Iran. Bush's "Greater Middle East" plan was initially designed to eliminate the threat to the Zionist regime and ensure its security. In contrast, the Zionist regime also plays a major role in supporting US regional policies. In the developments of West Asia, the Zionist regime is a safe and trusted option of the capitalist system that can maintain the existing order. In this regard, the military occupation of Iraq, in addition to destroying one of the most serious enemies of the Zionist regime, extends the security sphere of Tel Aviv to Baghdad and simultaneously confronts the threats of Iran and Hezbollah in Lebanon (Simber, 2010: 117-119).

At the same time, we must not forget that political Islam, centered on the Islamic Revolution of Iran, is one of the most important and inspiring sources for US opposition to Iran. The September 11 crisis enabled the United States to physically encircle Iran through the military occupation of Afghanistan and Iraq. But this occupation has a paradoxical aspect; because at the same time with the occupation of Iraq, the strategic ground for gaining power of more than one hundred and forty million Shiites in the region was provided under the leadership of the Islamic Republic of Iran (Simber and Ghorbani Sheikh Nashin, 2008: 198).

However, we must remember that the open and deep view of Shiite Islam is not in line with the view based on Salafi interpretation of Islam and the Qur'an, and Shiite Iranians and Iraqi Shiites are the first victims of this Salafi Islam extremism, but the US government insists to introduce Iran as the leader of terrorism in the region and at the level of the international system, and thus to isolate and limit it. US government men and policymakers see the root of terrorism in West Asia as Islamic-Iranian fundamentalism (Nasr, 2006: 30)

On the other hand, supporting the Palestinian cause and the liberation of Jerusalem has been one of the most important reasons for the Islamic Republic of Iran's stubbornness and hostility to the Zionist regime. In fact, the roots of this challenge have an ideological basis, and the Islamic Republic of Iran has already lost several of its senior commanders, such as Ahmad Motusalian, as a result of the movements of the occupying regime in Jerusalem. Also, the assassination of some Iranian nuclear scientists has increased this challenge to its maximum. The culmination of this issue was the martyrdom of several Iranian Revolutionary Guards in the Zionist attacks in Syria. Another fact is that the occupying regime in Jerusalem has one of the most fragile geopolitics in the region. In terms of security, this issue can be considered as a bedrock of instability for this regime, so that today, Hezbollah in Lebanon, Syria and Iraqi militias are considered as one of the biggest security threats of this regime (Pollack, 2017: 9)

The occupying regime in Jerusalem has taken several general approaches in order to retaliate against the policies of the Resistance Front:

1. Securing the borders of the Islamic Republic of Iran by resorting to terrorists entering the borders of Iran;
2. Development of espionage activities against the IRGC, especially in the field of missiles and military;
3. Assassination of IRGC military scientists and engineers such as Hassan Tehrani Moghaddam and...
4. Logistical and economic support to terrorist groups in the western and southeastern regions of Iran;
5. Incitement of regional and supra-regional allies in condemning the activities of the IRGC and its commanders;
6. Direct attack on Revolutionary Guards positions in some parts of West Asia, such as Syria;
7. Extensive media warfare and widespread propaganda against the IRGC;
8. Senior IRGC commanders threaten direct war (Juneau, 2017: 70)

Meanwhile, Saudi-centered Wahhabi Islam relations with the policies of the Islamic Republic of Iran as the ruler of the Shiite world are of great importance. Although these relations have been in full swing, at least since the victory of the Islamic Revolution in Iran, the origins of ideological rivalries based on mutual distrust have always been between the two countries. The turning point in Saudi foreign policy can be seen in maximizing the confrontation with Iran in all political, economic and security spheres at the regional level and in the international system. In this regard, Saudi Arabia was deeply concerned about the rise to power of Iran after the emergence of a Shiite state in Iraq and the developments in West Asia after the Islamic Awakening and the Iran nuclear deal known as JCPOA, so it intensified its policies. Challenges and tensions with the Islamic Republic of Iran and other Shiites in the region (Alishahi et al., 2017).

The Saudis revived ties with the United States during the Trump era, forming a regional and international coalition against Iran for allegedly supporting terrorism at the 2012 Riyadh summit, and in organizations such as the Arab League, the Gulf Cooperation Council, the Organization of the Islamic Conference and the United Nations put extensive propaganda and operational measures on the agenda against Iran and the axis of resistance, especially Hezbollah in Lebanon and the Houthis in Yemen. On the other hand, by sabotaging the lifting of the international community's economic sanctions against Iran in the post-JCPOA period, it has also tried to intensify economic pressures against Iran. Saudi Arabia even resorted to internal developments and creating unrest and social unrest in Iran through affiliated Salafi currents by explicitly announcing bin Salman that war would be brought to the borders of Iran (Masoudnia et al., 2016: 159).

In addition, by prioritizing the confrontation with Iran, with the emergence of the common interests of the Zionist-Saudi regime, the joint efforts of both to control Iran and become a regional hegemon due to the military conflict in Syria, Iraq and Yemen) increased. In this regard, the military and security leaders of the Zionist regime and Saudi Arabia met, so that even the head of Mossad reportedly met with the heads of the Saudi intelligence and national security service. Mossad chief Mirdagan also held talks with Riyadh from 2002 to 2010 to use Saudi airspace to launch a possible attack on Iran. The combination of these developments in Saudi Arabia's regional policies marks the beginning of a new era of approaches to safeguarding its domestic and regional interests by taking an aggressive approach to developments in West Asia which represents the adventures of new leaders (Rostami and Tara 2018: 126).

Utilizing Saudi economic potential:

Bin Salman had long supported Republican policies, which he said depended on American support, and he acknowledged that people like Trump had a commercial and economic personality. Sought macroeconomic support from the Republic. In this regard, during the Trump election campaign, the scenario of Muhammad bin Salman ascending the throne also has been kicked off. Recently, a document was released that revealed that Trump had promised to support bin Salman in exchange for Saudi money entering US markets. According to the document, shortly after Donald Trump was elected President of the United States, Mohammed bin Salman had given Trump a complete plan, most of which included contracts and hundreds of billions of dollars in investments in line with the goals of his campaign. According to the document, Mohammed bin Salman called the plan "Saudi Arabia's approach to strategic partnership with the United States" and the subtitle "Request to

the President-elect," and Trump agreed to implement it in several stages. The first clause of the plan is to increase Saudi Arabia's assets in the United States to \$ 2,000 billion over the next four years. The second clause is a commitment to coordinate with the Gulf states to establish a fund to finance US infrastructure projects worth \$ 50 billion to \$ 100 billion and to participate in investments in accordance with the priorities of the election program, and includes a large number of the agreement will include Saudi Arabia's commitments to Washington in the areas of investment and economic and strategic partnerships in the fields of energy and oil. The plan emphasizes that Saudi Arabia will contribute to the creation of 25 million jobs in the United States over the next 10 years.

The plan also proposes the creation of an American business district on the Red Sea coast under the supervision of American organizations. This trade zone could be America's gateway to Africa and West Asia. Under the plan, Saudi Arabia will provide the United States with a military base in the Red Sea.

The investment plan puts Saudi Arabia's assets in the United States at about \$ 1 trillion and strengthens social ties, and states that the development of Trump's military and arms deals to pursue his aggressive policies against the Islamic Republic of Iran must lead to major arms deals development with Saudi Arabia. According to Bin Salman, the use of such heavy costs may pave the way for the further development of the country's power in the region in order to suppress resistance movements such as Hezbollah in Lebanon, Ansarullah in Yemen and Hashad al-Shaabi in Iraq, and ultimately an important deterrent to the Islamic Republic of Iran. It is quite true that the Saudis had a history of buying weapons from the United States before bin Salman, but never in the military-political history of Saudi Arabia has such a volume of weapons been sold to the United States by the United States (Holland, 2017: 2)

In fact, by adopting such a policy, Bin Salman pursued several main goals:

- Increasing development of Saudi military power;
- Confrontation with the Islamic Republic of Iran, Hezbollah, Ansarullah and...
- The necessary economic guarantee to Trump, considering his economic-commercial personality (Trump) in order to implement the policies of the Republicans;
- Ensuring the stability and security of the Zionist regime to the United States in the event of war and providing the necessary cooperation with this regime due to the growing influence of the Islamic Republic of Iran in the region;
- Establishment of the Arab-Western NATO in order to counter the Iran-Russia alliance (Malsin, 2017: 1)

- Post-JCPOA action of the Islamic Republic of Iran

Although JCPOA was not designed to resolve regional issues, by creating an opportunity for Iran to return to the international community and paving the way for interaction between Iran and the West, it had created an opportunity for the two sides to talk to each other about other tense issues. However, for reasons that are not the subject of the present discussion, JCPOA could not open a path for Iran and the West in this regard, and in a situation where Iran itself could take the initiative in this regard and with its own hand in the crises in the region turn the winner in his talks on tensions with the West, which missed this golden opportunity due to the post-JCPOA performance of the Islamic Republic.

- Increasing pressure from the US domestic opposition

The fact is that Donald Trump is facing the most opposition and criticism from the American political spectrum today. The scope of these objections has even reached the ranks of radical neoconservatives such as George W. Bush. The culmination of opposition to Trump's extravagant policies is the question of his impeachment. Trump's achievements in foreign policy, especially in the economic field, with the People's Republic of China, the failure to reach a credible agreement with North Korea, the failure of US policies in West Asia, especially against the Islamic Republic of Iran in foreign policy, and the failure of Trump Regarding the US economic development, the abnormal situation of insurance and unemployment in this country and the recent case of disclosing Trump's conversation with Ukrainian officials in the case of Mr. Jobiden's son is one of the most important excuses for Democrats and other Trump opponents to justify him in the by-elections. The second is the US presidency. The failure to complete Iran's nuclear program and the failure of policies leading to the deal

of the century and the lack of specific achievements in US Middle East policies are some of the other major reasons why the US opposition is pushing Trump.

Conclusion:

Confrontation with Iran and the policies of the Islamic Republic of Iran in the region has been one of the main issues of Trump's foreign policy in the Middle East. In his campaigns, Trump has repeatedly criticized Barack Obama, who said his policies have made Iran more powerful in the region and a threat to the United States. He considers confronting Iranian military forces in the Persian Gulf and intensifying pressure on Iran to withdraw from regional policies as one of its main policies. However, the focus of Trump's policy on Iran can be seen as Iran's nuclear deal and countering it. Trump, like many Republicans, strongly opposed the Iran nuclear deal, calling it a challenge to the United States and its allies. He has sharply criticized the US diplomatic apparatus over the nuclear deal with Iran. Donald Trump is a Republican member of the US Christian right. This current, with its ideological and at the same time power-oriented attitude, believes in the return of the United States to the past of American rule and exceptionalism. Regarding the Islamic Republic of Iran, Trump believes in utilitarian policies and, while believing in countering Iran's regional influence and dealing with Iran's military adventure in the region, calls for a reconsideration of the UN Security Council through renegotiation, using multilateral economic pressures. This was considered as a kind of abolition or challenge of JCPOA by the United States by the Islamic Republic of Iran. The Islamic Republic of Iran, in the eyes of the United States and its regional allies (Saudi Arabia and Israel) after JCPOA, continued to be portrayed as a constant threat to international stability and order. (these countries share a common understanding of the Iranian threat and common interests, namely Challenging the regional hegemony of the Islamic Republic of Iran and persuading the United States, along with other secondary variables, to withdraw from the UN Security Council);

In other words, the debate over the notion of a security threat and actor has remained strong. In such a way that the content of the threat in the name of the Islamic Republic was constant at all times and its form changed. Before the implementation of JCPOA, the Islamic Republic of Iran was a terrorist threat, a threat to human rights and a nuclear threat, and after the nuclear deal, the feeling of JCPOA threat, the basis of the threat of regional hegemony and then the missile threat were built and this chain will continue. . After the withdrawal of the United States from the UN Security Council, the country intends to threaten the economic interests of Iran by attracting some forced, accompanied by a significant number of international actors and trading partners, and in fact engages Iran in a repetitive or consecutive game of sanctions. That the country either targets or surrenders and changes its behavior or resists the wishes of the sanctioning country, and this cycle continues until one of the parties decides to end the game. The nature of boycott games is repetitive and very erosive. The Islamic Republic of Iran is caught in the vicious circle of the security actor - the game of sanctions - negotiations.

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